

A Rank-Based Approach for Generating Synthetic Databases with Correlated Non-Normal Distributions: Application to Beef Cattle Methane Production

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Abstract: This study addresses the challenge of limited data availability in animal science, particularly in modeling complex biological processes such as methane emissions from ruminants. We propose a novel rank-based method for generating synthetic databases with correlated non-normal multivariate distributions aimed at enhancing the accuracy and reliability of predictive modeling tools. Our rank-based approach involves a four-step process: (1) fitting distributions to variables using normal or best-fit non-normal distributions, (2) generating synthetic databases, (3) preserving relationships among variables using Spearman correlations, and (4) cleaning datasets to ensure biological plausibility. We compare this method with copula-based approaches to maintain a pre-established correlation structure. The rank-based method demonstrated superior performance in preserving original distribution moments (mean, variance, skewness, kurtosis) and correlation structures compared to copula-based methods. We generated two synthetic databases (normal and non-normal distributions) and applied random forest (RF) and multiple linear regression (LM) analyses. RF regression outperformed LM in predicting methane emissions, showing higher R^2 values (0.927 vs. 0.622) and lower standard errors. However, cross-testing revealed that RF regressions exhibit high specificity to distribution types, underperforming when applied to data with differing distributions. In contrast, LM regressions showed robustness across different distribution types. Our findings highlight the importance of understanding distributional assumptions in regression techniques when generating synthetic databases. The study also underscores the potential of synthetic data in augmenting limited samples, addressing class imbalances, and simulating rare scenarios. While our method effectively preserves descriptive statistical properties, we acknowledge the possibility of introducing artificial (unknown) relationships within subsets of the synthetic database. This research uncovered a practical solution for creating realistic, statistically sound datasets when original data is scarce or sensitive. Its application in predicting methane emissions demonstrates the potential to enhance modeling accuracy in animal science. Future research directions include integrating this approach with deep learning, exploring real-world applications, and developing adaptive machine-learning models for diverse data distributions.

Keywords: Correlation preservation, Methane, Multiple linear regression, Non-normal distributions, Random forest, Synthetic data

Introduction

In lieu of the distinct purposes and applications of traditional (mechanistic, concept-based) and artificial intelligent (AI; data-driven) models, adapting traditional models to fit within an AI framework may not fully leverage the potential benefits of AI in agriculture.^[36; 110] Instead, AI-oriented models should be developed independently to capture the unique data-driven insights they offer and subsequently integrated with mechanistic models, yielding hybrid intelligent mechanistic models that describe the underlying principles of outcomes while handling massive amounts of data.^[111; 113] However, AI-oriented models rely on vast amounts of curated data, encompassing numerous variables and extensive records, which may not always be available for specific needs and simulations, particularly in animal science production.^[111] This scarcity of big data is not unique to animal science; it is also prevalent in the medical field due to privacy regulations and the rarity of certain diseases,^[1] in environmental science where data quality, measurement, and accessibility pose significant challenges,^[80; 114] and in economics due to privacy and proprietary data concerns,^[35] to name a few. Furthermore, the need for reliable and curated data, coupled with the challenges of proper data integration, adds another layer of complexity to an already strenuous situation. The limitations of real-world datasets necessitate innovative synthetic data generation methods across fields. These techniques aim to augment limited samples, safeguard sensitive information, rectify class imbalances, and simulate rare or hypothetical scenarios. Crucially, they strive to preserve the intricate relationships among variables, maintain statistical fidelity, and avoid introducing spurious correlations, thereby enhancing the robustness and applicability of data-driven models and analyses. In particular, the agricultural sector faces unique challenges in modeling complex biological processes, such as methane (CH₄) emissions from ruminants, where comprehensive datasets are often limited given the difficulties associated with their measurement in the field.^[114]

Although the definition of synthetic data continues to evolve, the concept of using computer-generated data to address specific tasks is well-established. This approach traces back to the pioneering work of Stanislaw Ulam and John von Neumann in the 1940s, who developed Monte Carlo simulation methods to model complex systems during World War II.^[15; 79; 121] Today, the landscape of synthetic data generation has expanded significantly, encompassing a wide array of advanced techniques. Deep learning (DL) architectures like generative adversarial networks (GAN) have revolutionized the production of highly realistic synthetic images, text, and medical data.^[44] Variational autoencoders (VAE) provide a probabilistic approach to generating new data points finding applications in image processing and anomaly detection.^[70] Other methods, such as agent-based econometric models^[18] and stochastic differential equations used to simulate physical or economic systems,^[23; 24] also contribute to synthetic data generation. More recent advancements include synthetic data vault (SDV), which uses probabilistic graphical models to generate multi-table relational data,^[91] and differential privacy (DP) techniques that add controlled noise to preserve individual privacy while maintaining statistical utility.^[34] Notably, Dwork et al. ^[33] introduced the concept of the reusable holdout. This method allows multiple analyses on the same dataset while preventing overfitting and maintaining the validity of results, which is particularly valuable when working with limited or sensitive data. These sophisticated algorithms create realistic and high-quality datasets applicable across various fields, particularly in medicine.^[43] In finance, synthetic data plays a crucial role in overcoming data-sharing limitations due to regulatory requirements and privacy concerns. It can help simulate market conditions, test trading algorithms without financial risk, and enable cross-departmental collaboration within financial institutions. In crop science, Akkem et al. ^[2] provided a comprehensive review of synthetic data generation in smart farming using GAN and VAE, highlighting the potential of these techniques in addressing data scarcity issues. As Assefa et al. ^[5] highlighted, synthetic

financial data generation faces unique challenges in creating realistic datasets, measuring similarities with actual data, and ensuring privacy compliance, all while navigating the complex regulatory landscape of the financial services industry. This approach not only facilitates internal data sharing but also opens up possibilities for broader research collaborations in the financial domain. For autonomous vehicle development, synthetic datasets are crucial in training and validating AI models, fostering safer and more efficient transportation solutions.^[43] While these tools excel in image processing and data imputation, there remains a pressing need to develop datasets that accurately capture existing relationships among variables to serve better diverse applications, such as in environmental science and social policy modeling^[86] and agricultural sciences when data is limited.

Several methods have been developed to generate synthetic databases using correlated, non-normally distributed data, addressing the limitations of traditional approaches that often assume normality. Qu et al.^[93] described an approach based on the work of Vale and Maurelli^[122], which generates data based on the first four moments (means, variances, skewness, and kurtosis) while considering the correlation among the independent variables. This method extends the multivariate normal distribution to accommodate non-normal data. However, it requires detailed information on the four moments for each independent variable, which can be challenging when the variables have distinct distributions (e.g., triangular, log-logistic, β -general). To address these limitations, Ruscio and Kaczetow^[101] proposed an iterative, trial-and-error process to sample from non-normal distributions while maintaining the desired correlation matrix. This approach offers more flexibility but can be computationally intensive for large datasets. Auerswald and Moshagen^[6] introduced a non-linear structural equation modeling approach that uses non-linear linking functions and covariance corrections to generate synthetic data with specified moments and correlation structures, providing a more flexible and robust solution. More recent advancements include the work of Xu and Veeramachaneni^[135], who proposed a method using Gaussian copulas to model complex dependencies between variables while preserving their distributions. This approach can handle mixed data types and capture non-linear relationships more effectively. Despite these advancements, there remains a need for approaches that effectively generate synthetic datasets by leveraging existing relational dependencies among variables, particularly when these variables deviate from the normal distribution assumptions. Furthermore, maintaining utility while ensuring privacy in synthetic data generation remains a critical challenge, especially in domains with sensitive information, such as healthcare and finance.^[62; 83] Such methods would not only preserve the inherent relationships among variables but also enhance the applicability and accuracy of synthetic datasets in various machine learning (ML) and simulation tasks.

The need for robust synthetic data generation methods is particularly evident in the field of agricultural science, where modeling complex biological processes often relies on limited datasets. A prime example of this challenge is in the study and prediction of CH₄ emissions from ruminants. Methane emissions from ruminants are a significant contributor to greenhouse gases, impacting global climate change. According to Tedeschi^[112] and Tedeschi and Beauchemin^[115], U.S. beef cattle alone emitted 22.6% of total agricultural emissions, representing about 2.2% of total anthropogenic emissions of CO₂ equivalent. Developing accurate predictive models for CH₄ production is crucial for devising effective mitigation strategies in animal agriculture. However, the complexity of the biological processes involved and the limitations in data collection^[63; 114] often result in datasets that are insufficient for modern AI modeling approaches. The objective of this paper is to address this challenge by proposing a robust synthetic data generation method that accommodates the complexities of multivariate non-normal distributions, which are commonly found in agricultural datasets but often neglected. We present a simple yet effective method for creating synthetic databases, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of predictive modeling tools such as random forest regression and simple linear multivariate regressions. To illustrate the practical application of this method, an existing CH₄ production database from beef cattle is used as a case

study, demonstrating how synthetic data can improve model predictions and provide deeper insights into CH₄ emissions from ruminants. Building upon this initial work, we have developed a web-based application of this technology at <https://www.nutritionmodels.com/methane.html>. This interactive web tool serves as a practical interface for researchers, nutritionists, and livestock managers to apply our CH₄ prediction model to their specific scenarios.

Material and Methods

Original Database

The original database was compiled from studies gathered by Galyean et al. [40], supplemented with additional published research listed in Appendix 1. The comprehensive dataset comprises 63 studies (34 initial and 29 additional), totaling 263 records. No specific selection criteria were applied to ensure a generalized database with broad variability, reflecting the original non-normal distribution of the variables of interest. The dataset includes eight independent variables: body weight (BW, kg), dry matter (DM) intake (DMI, kg/d), crude protein (CP, %DM), neutral detergent fiber (NDF, %DM), ether extract (EE, %DM), starch (%DM), acid detergent fiber (ADF, %DM), and ash (%DM), with CH₄ production (g/d), i.e., emission, as the dependent variable. Figure 1 has the histogram and density plots and best-fit non-linear distribution for CH₄, while Supplement 1 presents the same graphical information for the independent variables. It is crucial to note that the reported values are averages of measured values, representing estimated true population means. Consequently, the actual variability in the population may be more considerable than depicted, as the averaging process tends to smooth out extreme values and natural

Figure 1. Histogram and density plots of methane (CH₄, g/d) from the literature-gathered database. The blue bars represent the histogram, the orange shade indicates the density plot of the original data, the green line illustrates the density plot of the fitted data using the best-fit distribution shown at the top of the plot, and the vertical lines from left to right denote the minimum (min), mean – 1 SD, mean, mean + 1 SD, and maximum (max) values in the literature-gathered database.

variations. This limitation should be considered when interpreting results and extrapolating findings to broader contexts.

Synthetic Databases

The *gamlss* package [97; 104] of R v. 4.4.1 [94] was used to create synthetic databases. The process involved the following four steps. Step 1: for each variable in the dataset, distributions were fitted using either a normal distribution assumption or the best-fit distribution selected from over 100 different types available in the *fitDist* function of the *gamlss* package. It was implemented as shown in Appendix 2. Step 2: this fitting process resulted in two synthetic databases, each containing 20,000 records. One database was generated using only normal distributions for each variable. The other database used the best-fit distributions for each variable, which could include normal distributions as well as other types. Step 3: Spearman correlations were calculated a priori using the *cor* function of R to preserve the relationships among variables. These correlations were then applied to the synthetic datasets to ensure that the original variable relationships were maintained. It was implemented as shown in Appendix 3. Step 4: the synthetic datasets were cleaned to ensure consistency and biological plausibility based on the following criteria: (1) CP, EE, starch, NDF, ADF, and ash had to be greater than zero and less than 100; (2) ADF values had to be less than NDF values; and (3) the sum of CP, EE, ash, NDF, and starch had to be less than 100. These steps ensured that the synthetic datasets closely mirrored the characteristics of the original data while maintaining the necessary statistical relationships and realistic constraints.

Correlation for Nonnormally Distributed Variables

The Cholesky decomposition, first introduced by André-Louis Cholesky in the early 20th century,^[60] is a mathematical technique primarily used for decomposing positive definite matrices. It is commonly employed to generate correlated normal random variables in the context of multivariate normal distributions.^[42] However, for nonnormal distributions, the direct application of Cholesky decomposition alone is insufficient to maintain the desired correlation structure. This limitation arises because the decomposition assumes normality, and directly applying it to nonnormal distributed variables may lead to distorted correlations. To address this issue and effectively generate correlated nonnormal variables, two alternative methods were compared in this study.

Rank-based method

This method is based on four steps: normal data generation, correlation imposition, ranking maps, and allocation assignment. It starts by generating uncorrelated normally distributed variables, and the Cholesky decomposition is applied to these variables to achieve the desired correlation. Then, the ranks of the values in each normally distributed variable are obtained. Finally, the original nonnormally distributed variables are reorganized (i.e., sorted) according to the ranks of the corresponding normally distributed variables that have undergone the Cholesky decomposition. Appendix 3 contains the R script code used to obtain the Cholesky decomposition for nonnormally distributed variables in our simulations. This simple and computationally efficient approach aims to have non-normal variables retain their original distributions while achieving the desired correlation. However, there may be limited flexibility in controlling the degree of non-normality, and this method may not fully retain the original Spearman correlation. Additionally, it is necessary to investigate whether the Cholesky decomposition and re-ranking process accurately replicates the desired correlation and distribution moments, including mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis.

Copula and structural equation modeling methods

Various methods exist to correlate multivariate non-normal distributions, including copulas and non-linear structural equation modeling (SEM). The copula method, widely used for modeling dependencies between variables,^[41; 84] involves a multi-step process: (1) generating synthetic data for each variable using best-fit non-normal distributions, (2) converting these to uniform distributions via the empirical cumulative distribution function, (3) transforming them to normally distributed marginals using the inverse normal cumulative distribution function, (4) adjusting the correlation structure iteratively to match the desired correlation matrix using Cholesky decomposition, (5) matching the ranks of the adjusted data to the ranks of the original non-normal data, and (6) iteratively checking to confirm convergence. This process aims to ensure that the data retains the original distributions while achieving the desired correlations. The non-linear SEM method^[6] generates synthetic data with specified moments using a different approach: (1) utilizing non-linear linking functions and covariance corrections to adjust initial data, (2) achieving the desired correlation structure, including specific higher moments like skewness and kurtosis, and (3) iteratively adjusting to ensure the final synthetic data closely match the target distributions and correlations specified in the model. Both methods aim to preserve the complex relationships and distributions of the original data while generating synthetic datasets that accurately reflect these characteristics. For the sake of comparison with the rank-based method, the R script code of an application of the copula-based method is shown in Appendix 3.

Evaluation of distribution moments and correlations

To evaluate the preservation of the original non-normal distributions, including skewness and kurtosis, while imposing a desired correlation structure using the rank-based and copula methods, we generated synthetic databases comprising three variables, each following a distinct non-normal distribution (chi-square, beta, and log-normal), with 5,000 samples across 100 iterations. Appendix 4 has the R script code, showing a predefined positive-definite correlation matrix used for this simulation. Specifically, var1 was generated from a chi-square distribution with 2 degrees of freedom, var2 was generated from a beta distribution with shape parameters $a=2$ and $b=5$, and var3 was generated from a log-normal distribution with a mean of zero and a standard deviation (SD) of 1. Furthermore, we compared the pre-established Spearman correlation with the Spearman correlation of these distributions after re-ranking them using our method across all 100 iterations.

Regression Fitting, Cross-testing, and Adequacy

Predictive regressions

Random Forest (RF) and Multiple Linear Regression (LM) analyses were performed on the synthetic databases to evaluate their predictive capabilities for CH₄ emissions. The RF regression was implemented using the *randomForest* package^[19] in R v. 4.4.1,^[94] with 150 trees and four randomly sampled variables as candidates at each split. This configuration was chosen based on preliminary analyses that showed optimal performance with these parameters. For the LM, we employed the ordinary least-squares method using the *lm* function in R v. 4.4.1.^[94]

Cross-testing

To assess the robustness and generalizability of the models, we conducted a cross-testing analysis. This involved applying regressions developed on the normally distributed synthetic database to the non-normally distributed synthetic database and vice versa. This cross-testing approach allows for a more comprehensive evaluation of model performance across different data distributions.

Gini importance plots

To assess the relative importance of predictor variables in the RF model, we utilized two key indices: predictive accuracy score (PAS) and the square error reduction (SER). The PAS measures of a variable's contribution to the model's predictive accuracy. It is calculated as the percentage increase in mean squared error (MSE) when the variable's values are randomly permuted. A higher PAS indicates that the variable is more crucial for maintaining the model's predictive accuracy. The PAS is also known as mean decrease in accuracy in classification tasks to measure how much the model's accuracy decreases when a variable is excluded, with higher values indicating greater importance.^[19] The SER is analogous to the mean decrease in Gini for classification tasks, and it quantifies the total decrease in node impurity from splits over a given variable, averaged across all trees. In regression contexts, SER (i.e., node impurity) is measured by the residual sum of squares; thus, its unit is the square unit of the dependent variable (i.e., daily CH₄ emission, g²/d²). Higher SER values suggest a variable's effectiveness in creating homogeneous groups (i.e., high precision) within the decision trees of the random forest. These measures offer complementary insights: PAS focuses on predictive accuracy, while SER reflects the variable's role in the tree structure (i.e., precision). Variables with higher SER values are considered more important in the model's decision-making process, while variables with higher PAS values increases the accuracy of the predictions. Strobl et al.^[105] noted that these importance measures can be influenced by correlations between predictor variables and differences in variable scales. The Gini importance plot displays the PAS and the SER values for each feature, and the variables are typically sorted in descending order of SER. This allows for a straightforward visual interpretation of feature importance, where features at the top of the plot are the most influential in the model's predictions. However, it is essential to note that while Gini importance provides valuable insights, it can be biased towards high-cardinality features and does not indicate the direction (positive or negative) of a feature's influence.^[106] Therefore, we interpret these plots in conjunction with other model adequacy metrics to gain a comprehensive understanding of our RF model's behavior and the underlying relationships in our data.

Prediction adequacy

The predictive accuracy of the CH₄ emission models was evaluated using a suite of statistical measures, as recommended by Tedeschi^[109]. These included mean bias (MB) to assess systematic over- or under-prediction; mean square error of prediction (MSEP) and its root (RMSEP) to quantify overall prediction error; concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) and its accuracy estimate (Cb) to evaluate the agreement between predicted and observed values; mean square error (MSE) which was further decomposed into mean bias, slope bias, and random errors to provide insights into the sources of prediction error; and Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) to compare model fit while accounting for model complexity. This comprehensive set of statistical measures provides a robust framework for assessing and comparing the performance of the RF and LM models across different synthetic data distributions.

Results and Discussion

Distribution Moments and Correlations

Distribution moments

Based on our evaluation of the distribution moments and correlation across the 100 iterations (Appendix 4; data not shown) for the rank-based method, the mean of the original and correlated data was preserved

for each distribution (chi-square, beta, and log-normal), indicating that the rank-based method effectively maintains the mean. The variance of the original and correlated data also remained consistent, showing that the method did not distort the spread of the data. The skewness values of the original and correlated data were very similar, indicating that the method preserves the asymmetry of the distributions. The kurtosis values of the original and correlated data matched closely, demonstrating that the method retains both the tail behavior and the central peak characteristics (i.e., peakedness) of the distributions. Over the 100 iterations, the differences between the original correlation (i.e., the pre-established matrix) and the effective correlation using the rank-based method varied from -0.0271 to 0.0428 for var1-var2, -0.174 to 0.0455 for var1-var3, and -0.0219 to 0.0419 for var2-var3. Our rank-based method (Appendix 3) to correlate multivariate non-normal distributions effectively maintained the mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis of the original non-normal distributions while imposing the desired correlation structure. Similarly, the copula-based approach (Appendix 3) was able to maintain the moments of the original and correlated data. However, the copula-based approach showed more variability and less precision in maintaining the desired Spearman correlations. The differences between the original correlation (i.e., the pre-established matrix) and the effective correlation using the copula-based method varied from -0.488 to 1 for var1-var2, -0.689 to 0.464 for var1-var3, and -0.599 to 0.357 for var2-var3. This method might be more suited for maintaining Pearson correlations rather than Spearman correlations, especially when applied to non-normal data. The large discrepancies in the Spearman correlations between the original and correlated data are intriguing and cast doubt on the ability of copula-based methods to yield pre-established correlated non-normally distributed variables adequately. It is also likely that the implementation in Appendix 3 needs further refinement. When using a variable correlation matrix instead of the pre-established matrix, the discrepancies increased further. This finding confirms that the rank-based method provides reasonable control over the higher moments of the distributions beyond just rank correlation.

Spearman correlation matrix

The original Spearman correlation matrix (COR1) of the literature-gathered database to predict CH₄ emissions in beef cattle (n = 263 records; Appendix 1) is shown in Eq. [1]. Similarly, the Spearman correlation matrix (COR2) of the synthetic database (n = 9,484; after the removal of outliers and non-conforming data points) is shown in Eq. [2]. The synthetic database was developed using the best-fit non-normal distributions (*getDist* shown in Appendix 3) for each variable, and their values were ranked using the methodology outlined in Appendix 3 (*correlate_using_ranks* function).

As noted by Akkem et al. [2], a fundamental challenge in generating synthetic crop data lies in accurately capturing the intricate temporal and spatial dependencies inherent in crop growth and environmental factors. This challenge underscores the critical importance of ensuring that the synthetic data generation process preserves existing relationships among variables while avoiding the introduction of spurious correlations or artificial patterns. In the context of generating synthetic databases, maintaining this delicate balance is crucial, as the effectiveness of these systems relies heavily on the authenticity and representativeness of the underlying data. In our case, both matrices exhibit similar overall structures, indicating that the synthetic data generation method has successfully preserved the general pattern of correlations without adding additional patterns (i.e., correlation matrices are very similar). The majority of the differences between COR1 and COR2 are minor, suggesting that the method effectively maintains the original correlation structure. A few correlations exhibit moderate differences, such as those involving CP with BW, starch with NDF, and ash with BW. These differences, while noticeable, are not significant enough to drastically impact the overall distribution structure. Several correlations show negligible differences, suggesting that the synthetic data closely approximates the original data's correlation structure in many instances. The minor and negligible differences indicate that the synthetic data

generation method is robust and does not significantly alter the distribution's structure. The preservation of correlation, along with mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis, indicates that the synthetic data maintains the statistical properties of the original data. While moderate differences in some correlations might slightly affect specific relationships between variables, these are not widespread, and the overall impact on the distribution is likely minor.

$$COR1 = \begin{matrix} & ADF & Ash & BW & CH_4 & CP & DMI & EE & NDF & Starch \\ \begin{matrix} ADF \\ Ash \\ BW \\ CH_4 \\ CP \\ DMI \\ EE \\ NDF \\ Starch \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 1.00 & 0.58 & -0.18 & 0.39 & 0.55 & 0.00 & -0.12 & 0.91 & -0.79 \\ 0.58 & 1.00 & -0.02 & 0.41 & 0.48 & 0.16 & -0.44 & 0.61 & -0.65 \\ -0.18 & -0.02 & 1.00 & 0.35 & -0.10 & 0.65 & -0.34 & -0.17 & 0.36 \\ 0.39 & 0.41 & 0.35 & 1.00 & 0.39 & 0.63 & -0.36 & 0.35 & -0.39 \\ 0.55 & 0.48 & -0.10 & 0.39 & 1.00 & 0.24 & -0.14 & 0.48 & -0.67 \\ 0.00 & 0.16 & 0.65 & 0.63 & 0.24 & 1.00 & -0.24 & 0.04 & -0.03 \\ -0.12 & -0.44 & -0.34 & -0.36 & -0.14 & -0.24 & 1.00 & -0.24 & 0.11 \\ 0.91 & 0.61 & -0.17 & 0.35 & 0.48 & 0.04 & -0.24 & 1.00 & -0.80 \\ -0.79 & -0.65 & 0.36 & -0.39 & -0.67 & -0.03 & 0.11 & -0.80 & 1.00 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix} \quad \text{Eq. [1]}$$

$$COR2 = \begin{matrix} & ADF & Ash & BW & CH_4 & CP & DMI & EE & NDF & Starch \\ \begin{matrix} ADF \\ Ash \\ BW \\ CH_4 \\ CP \\ DMI \\ EE \\ NDF \\ Starch \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 1.00 & 0.56 & -0.16 & 0.38 & 0.53 & 0.01 & -0.12 & 0.90 & -0.78 \\ 0.56 & 1.00 & 0.00 & 0.40 & 0.46 & 0.16 & -0.43 & 0.59 & -0.63 \\ -0.16 & 0.00 & 1.00 & 0.35 & -0.06 & 0.64 & -0.34 & -0.15 & 0.32 \\ 0.38 & 0.40 & 0.35 & 1.00 & 0.38 & 0.62 & -0.36 & 0.34 & -0.38 \\ 0.53 & 0.46 & -0.06 & 0.38 & 1.00 & 0.25 & -0.15 & 0.46 & -0.64 \\ 0.01 & 0.16 & 0.64 & 0.62 & 0.25 & 1.00 & -0.23 & 0.04 & -0.03 \\ -0.12 & -0.43 & -0.34 & -0.36 & -0.15 & -0.23 & 1.00 & -0.23 & 0.11 \\ 0.90 & 0.59 & -0.15 & 0.34 & 0.46 & 0.04 & -0.23 & 1.00 & -0.80 \\ -0.78 & -0.63 & 0.32 & -0.38 & -0.64 & -0.03 & 0.11 & -0.80 & 1.00 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix} \quad \text{Eq. [2]}$$

Where ADF is acid detergent fiber, % dry matter (DM); Ash is % DM; BW is body weight, kg; CP is crude protein, % DM; DMI is DM intake, kg/d; EE is ether extract, % DM; NDF is neutral detergent fiber, % DM; and Starch is % DM.

When evaluating the Spearman correlations between the original and synthetic data generated over 100 iterations for chi-square, beta, and log-normal distributions (data not shown), we observed a difference of around 0.25 between the chi-square and beta distributions, while the differences between chi-square and log-normal, as well as beta and log-normal, were less than 0.1 for the rank-based method. The histograms of the differences in Spearman correlations between the original and correlated data are centered around zero, indicating that the rank-based method closely preserves the correlation structure. Conversely, the copula-based method showed more significant and inconsistent differences. The histograms of the differences in Spearman correlations for the copula-based method displayed more significant variability, indicating less precision in maintaining the desired correlation structure (data not shown).

However, it is crucial to note that our analyses, while comprehensive in examining overall statistical properties and correlations, do not preclude the possibility of inadvertently creating artificial relationships within subsets of the synthetic database. This limitation arises from the inherent complexity of multivariate datasets and the potential for subtle interactions that broader statistical measures may not capture. Xu et al. ^[134], in their work on modeling tabular data using Conditional GAN, highlighted the difficulties in generating synthetic data that faithfully preserves the statistical properties of the original

dataset. Future work should involve more granular analyses of variable interactions, possibly employing techniques such as partial correlation analysis or advanced ML methods for detecting complex, non-linear relationships. Additionally, field experts could provide valuable insights into the practical implications of any artificial relationships that may have been introduced during the synthetic data generation process.

Predicting Methane Emissions

Figure 2 shows scatter plots comparing the observed CH₄ values from the synthetic dataset with the predicted CH₄ emissions using LM and RF regressions. Figure 2A presents the results under the assumption that all key variables follow a normal distribution, while Figure 2B presents the results without the assumption that all key variables follow normal distributions. Note that some variables might follow normal distribution naturally. The RF regression yielded a higher R² (0.927) compared to the LM (0.622 and 0.618), regardless of the assumed distributions of the critical variables. Additionally, the RF regression had approximately half the standard error (SE) of the regression compared to the LM regressions for both normal (Figure 2A) and non-normal (Figure 2B) distributions. The AIC was also lower for the RF than for the LM regressions. Table 1 provides further adequacy statistics, reinforcing the finding that the RF regression outperformed the LM regression in predicting CH₄ emissions from the synthetic database. Because these are fitting regressions, one would expect the means of the observed and predicted independent variables (i.e., CH₄) to be nearly identical, resulting in a mean bias (MB) close to zero, which is confirmed by the results (Table 1). However, the mean squared error (MSE) for the RF regressions was approximately 19% of that for the LM regressions under both conditions (normal and non-normal distributions). Furthermore, while 100% of the MSE for the LM regressions was due to random errors, the RF regressions had about 19% of the MSE attributable to slope bias.

Figure 3 depicts the Gini importance plots for RF regressions under the assumption that all key variables follow a normal distribution (Figure 3A) or without the assumption that all key variables follow normal distributions (Figure 3B). In both distribution scenarios, DMI emerged as the most influential predictor based on PAS (normal: 39.80%, non-normal: 38.89%), meaning that randomly shuffling DMI values while keeping other variables unchanged increased the model's MSE by 39.80% in the normal distribution scenario and 38.89% in the non-normal distribution scenario; thus, decreasing model's accuracy. This aligns with findings by Hristov et al. [63], who identified DMI as a primary driver of enteric CH₄ emissions in cattle. The EE showed consistent importance across both distributions (normal: 32.05%, non-normal: 32.80%), supporting Grainger and Beauchemin's [45] observations on the impact of dietary lipids on CH₄ production. Interestingly, the importance of fiber components differed between the two distributions. In the non-normal distribution model, ADF showed increased importance (PAS: 31.42% vs. 28.56% in the normal distribution), while NDF importance also increased (PAS: 23.53% vs. 16.13%). This shift suggests that accounting for non-normality may better capture the complex relationship between fiber content and CH₄ emissions. This aligns with findings from Appuhamy et al. [3], who noted that dietary NDF concentration was one of the most frequently appearing feed variables in evaluated CH₄ prediction models. Van Soest [123] also emphasized the critical role of fiber in ruminant nutrition and its impact on CH₄ production. The SER values provide a complementary perspective. In both distributions, NDF and ADF showed the highest SER values, underscoring the critical role of fiber in determining node purity in the RF model. However, the relative importance of these variables shifted, with ADF showing higher SER in the non-normal model (5,733,672 vs. 4,770,052 in normal), while NDF's SER decreased (3,023,372 vs.

Figure 2. Relationship between observed (Y-axis) and predicted (X-axis) methane (g/d) using multiple linear regression and random forest regression, assuming (A) normal and (B) non-normal distributions of the independent variables.

5,381,872). The CP and starch showed reduced importance in the non-normal model based on PAS (CP: 15.96% vs. 20.66%; starch: 26.51% vs. 32.79%). This suggests that assuming normality might overestimate the impact of these nutrients on CH₄ emissions. These findings align with Dijkstra et al. [32], who noted that increasing dietary CP content generally has little effect on CH₄ production. The variable importance of starch across our models suggests a complex relationship with CH₄ emissions. While Hatew et al. [56] reported that the effect of starch source on CH₄ production was not consistent, our results indicate that the importance of starch may be overestimated when assuming normal distribution. The BW maintained relatively consistent importance across both models in terms of PAS (normal: 21.85%, non-normal: 18.49%), supporting its inclusion as a stable predictor in CH₄ emission models [82], likely because the relationship between DMI and BW is represented by a linear relationship (i.e., power of 1) [123] though Ketelaars and Tolkamp [69] showed evidence that DMI increases

proportionally to the maintenance requirement (i.e., to the metabolic body weight; power of 0.75). The discrepancies in variable importance between the two distribution assumptions highlight the sensitivity of RF models to underlying data distributions. This underscores the importance of carefully considering

Figure 3. The Gini importance plot showing the increase in mean square error if the variable is removed from the model (predictive accuracy score, %; line length) and the how effectively a variable reduces residual square error when used for splitting in the random forest's decision trees (square error reduction, (g/d)²; point size), assuming (A) normal and (B) non-normal distributions of the variables.

data distribution when interpreting model results, particularly in complex biological systems like ruminant CH₄ production. Our findings suggest that models assuming non-normal distributions may provide a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing CH₄ emissions, especially concerning dietary fiber content. These results emphasize the critical need to consider data distribution when developing predictive models for CH₄ emissions. Assuming normality may lead to misinterpretation of the relative importance of certain dietary components, potentially impacting the accuracy of CH₄ prediction models and subsequent mitigation strategies in ruminant production systems.

Cross-testing analysis

Table 1 also has the adequacy statistics for the cross-testing analysis. In this analysis, LM and RF regressions developed under non-normal distribution conditions were

used to predict CH₄ using a synthetic database created under normal distribution conditions of the independent and dependent variables, and vice-versa. In the first scenario (non-normal regressions with normal distribution database), the RF regression underperformed compared to the LM regression.

Although the MSE was similar between the RF (1130.5) and LM (1030.3) regressions, the RF regression had an MB of -1.05 g/d compared to 0.11 g/d for the LM regression. Similarly, in the second scenario (normal regressions with non-normal distribution database), the MSE was similar between RF (1091.2) and LM (1015.9) regressions, but the MB was greater for the RF (1.91 g/d) than for the LM (-1.22 g/d) regressions. Notably, there was a sign exchange in the MB during these cross-testing analyses. The cross-testing results in Table 1 suggest that the adequacy statistics for the LM regressions are independent of the nature of the distribution of the independent and dependent variables. In contrast, the RF regressions exhibit high specificity; RF regressions developed using normal distribution are only suitable for normal distribution predictions, and those developed using non-normal distributions are only suitable for predictions with synthetic databases generated from non-normal distributions of the independent and dependent variables. The LM regressions appeared to be robust to the distribution type of the synthetic database used for both development and evaluation purposes. Conversely, the RF regressions underperformed (as indicated by MB values far from zero, higher MSE, higher AIC, and lower R²; Table 1) when the distribution type of the development and evaluation of synthetic databases differed.

Table 1. Diverse fitting and predictive statistics of 2 x 2 combination for data generation and regression fitting using normal and nonnormal distributions for linear model (LM) or random forest (RF) regressions.

Items ⁽¹⁾	Normal Distributions				Nonnormal Distributions			
	Normal Regressions		Non-normal Regressions		Normal Regression		Non-normal Regressions	
	RF	LM	RF	LM	RF	LM	RF	LM
N	8542	8542	8542	8542	9484	9484	9484	9484
Mean								
Predicted	128.5	128.6	129.7	128.5	126.4	129.6	128.5	128.4
Observed	128.6	128.6	128.6	128.6	128.4	128.4	128.4	128.4
MB	0.07	0.00	-1.05	0.11	1.91	-1.22	-0.17	0.00
SD								
Predicted	44.1	40.8	39.4	41.1	38.7	39.9	43.2	39.9
Observed	51.7	51.7	51.7	51.7	50.8	50.8	50.8	50.8
RMSE ⁽²⁾	14.0	31.8	33.6	32.1	33.0	31.9	13.7	31.4
r ²	0.93	0.62	0.58	0.61	0.58	0.61	0.93	0.62
CCC	0.96	0.77	0.73	0.76	0.73	0.76	0.96	0.76
C _b	0.99	0.97	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.97	0.99	0.97
MSE ⁽²⁾	195.5	1011.0	1130.5	1030.3	1091.2	1015.9	188.7	984.7
MB,%	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0
Slope,%	18.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	19.3	0.0
Random,%	81.1	100.0	99.9	100.0	99.7	99.8	80.7	100.0
AIC	70505	83361	85495	92301	94456	83361	77813	92301

⁽¹⁾ AIC = Akaike's Information Criterion, CCC = concordance correlation coefficient, C_b = accuracy, MB = mean bias, MSE = mean square error, r² = coefficient of determination, RMSE = root of the mean square error, and SD = standard deviation.

⁽²⁾ For statistical models with large databases, the MSEP and MSE tend to yield similar values as $MSE = MSEP \times n / (n - p)$; where p is number of parameters. The ratio $n / (n - p)$ is close to 1 for $n = 10,000$ and $p = 9$.

These findings highlight the importance of understanding the distributional assumptions behind different regression techniques when generating synthetic databases. Multiple linear regression models showed robustness across different distribution types, making them a more flexible choice when the distribution of data may vary. In contrast, RF regressions, while generally more accurate within the same distribution type, exhibited significant performance drops when applied to data with differing distributions. Various techniques exist for generating synthetic databases, each with its strengths and limitations. Methods such as GAN^[44] and VAE^[70] have gained popularity for creating high-fidelity synthetic data, particularly in fields like image processing and anomaly detection.

These DL approaches have shown a remarkable ability to capture complex data distributions and generate realistic synthetic samples. For instance, Esteban et al. ^[37] demonstrated the use of GAN in generating synthetic electronic health records that preserved the statistical properties of the original data while ensuring patient privacy. However, these methods often require large amounts of data and computational resources, which might not be practical for all applications, especially in fields with limited data availability, such as animal science. Another common approach involves using copula-based methods, which can model dependencies between variables without assuming a specific marginal distribution.^[84] This can be advantageous when dealing with non-normal data, as it provides flexibility in maintaining the original data structure. Patki et al. ^[91] utilized copula-based methods in their SDV framework, demonstrating its effectiveness in generating synthetic relational databases that preserve statistical properties and relationships across multiple tables. However, the complexity of copula models and the computational burden they impose can be challenging to manage, especially for high-dimensional datasets. Furthermore, in our preliminary analysis of the copula-based method (Appendix 3), it had more variability in preserving the original distribution moments compared to the rank-based method, the histograms of the differences in Spearman correlations between the original and correlated data for the copula-based method showed more spread, indicating less precision in maintaining the desired correlation structure, and although the copula method provides flexibility in modeling dependencies between variables, it was more complex and computationally intensive than the rank-based method. Interestingly and somewhat unexpectedly, the copula-based method did not perform as well as the rank-based method in terms of preserving the correlations of the original data, suggesting that while the copula-based approach is theoretically robust and flexible, in practice, it may introduce more variability and require substantial computational resources, making the rank-based method a more efficient and reliable choice for applications with constraints similar to ours.

In our study, the rank-based method used to generate synthetic data ensured that the non-normal characteristics of the original data were preserved. This method demonstrated a balance between simplicity and effectiveness, especially when the goal is to maintain the relational structure of the variables. Similar to our approach, Ruscio and Kaczetow ^[101] proposed an iterative algorithm for generating multivariate, non-normal data with specified intercorrelations, which has shown good performance in preserving both univariate distributions and correlations. The performance of RF regressions, although highly specific to the distribution type, underscores the potential need for hybrid approaches that combine the robustness of LM with the precision of RF under specific conditions. This aligns with recent trends in ensemble methods and hybrid models. For example, Zhang and Mahadevan ^[136] proposed a hybrid approach combining copula-based modeling with ML techniques for uncertainty quantification in engineering applications, demonstrating improved performance over traditional methods.

Future research could explore integrating these techniques to leverage their respective strengths, potentially developing more versatile models capable of handling diverse data distributions. For instance, combining the rank-based method with elements of DL architectures could potentially yield a more robust

and flexible synthetic data generation framework. Additionally, investigating the application of these methods in real-world scenarios beyond synthetic datasets would provide deeper insights into their practical utility and limitations. Furthermore, the field of DP^[34] offers promising avenues for generating synthetic data that not only preserves statistical properties but also provides strong privacy guarantees. Integrating differential privacy techniques with our rank-based method could enhance the utility of synthetic data for sensitive applications, such as those involving medical or financial data. Lastly, the specificity of RF regressions to distribution types observed in our study suggests a need for adaptive ML models that can automatically adjust to different data distributions. Recent advancements in transfer learning and domain adaptation techniques^[131] could potentially be applied to develop more flexible RF models that maintain high performance across varying data distributions.

Considerations about the Sample Size on Overfitting and Overconfidence

Another important consideration is the sample size of the synthetic database. We initially generated a 20,000-record synthetic database but ended up with approximately 10,000 usable records (Table 1) after removing spurious and non-biological data that were generated randomly. This reduction occurred due to the strict biological constraints we imposed to ensure the synthetic data accurately reflected real-world scenarios. For instance, we removed records where the sum of dietary components exceeded 100% or where ADF values were higher than NDF values, which are technically possible in real life due to limitations in the methodology of these fiber components,^[116; 123] but theoretically and biologically flawed. The final sample size of around 10,000 records is particularly relevant in the context of our regression analyses. For RF models, this sample size is generally considered sufficient to achieve stable and reliable results.^[90; 92] Oshiro et al.^[90] found that the performance of RF models tends to stabilize after about 128 trees, and our use of 150 trees aligns well with this finding. LM, the sample size is more than adequate, as the rule of thumb suggests a minimum of 10-20 observations per predictor variable.^[55; 118] Our cross-testing approach, where we applied models developed on normally distributed data to non-normally distributed data and vice versa, further validates the robustness of our sample size. This method allows us to assess how well the models generalize across different data distributions, which is crucial given the potential variability in real-world data. While the reduction in sample size from 20,000 to 10,000 records might seem substantial, it actually demonstrates the rigor of our data-cleaning process and ensures that our synthetic data closely mimics the biological constraints of real-world systems.

On the other hand, a point of concern is that a large sample size (i.e., 10,000 data points) used in our synthetic database for both LM and RF regressions can provide robust statistical power, but it may also lead to potential issues in model interpretation and performance evaluation. In the context of linear regression, it can lead to an inflation of goodness-of-fit measures and potentially misleading interpretations of model performance. As sample size increases, even minor effects can become statistically significant, potentially leading to over-interpretation of weak relationships.^[76; 132] Similarly, as sample size increases, the coefficient of determination (R^2 or r^2) tends to stabilize around the population value; it may appear impressively high even when the predictive power of the model is limited.^[77] This phenomenon is particularly relevant in our study, where the LM model showed consistent performance across different data distributions. For large samples, traditional goodness-of-fit measures may become less informative, and alternative metrics focusing on predictive performance should be considered, even considering the regressor variables as random.^[21] Future evaluations should focus on the effect sizes and practical significance rather than solely on statistical significance;^[107] adopt the use of adjusted R^2 or other less sensitive sample size metrics,^[103] such as the robust R^2 ,^[109] and consider the use of regularization techniques,^[38] such as lasso and ridge regressions, to prevent overfitting issues^[57] in large databases.

Similarly, for RF models, the risk of overfitting with large datasets is a significant concern. While RF is generally robust against overfitting due to its ensemble nature, the use of a large synthetic dataset may still lead to models that capture noise rather than true underlying patterns. Oshiro et al.^[90] reported that while increasing the number of trees generally improves performance, there is a point of diminishing returns, typically around 128 trees. In our study, the high R^2 values (0.927) observed for RF models, while indicative of good performance, could potentially be a result of overfitting to the synthetic data. Overfitting in RF might be mitigated by utilizing pruning techniques to reduce complexity in individual trees^[20] or employing k-fold cross-validation or out-of-bag error estimates to provide a more realistic assessment of model performance.^[19]

In fact, adding more data may backfire because RF may make incorrect predictions with a high degree of confidence (i.e., high R^2), mainly if the distribution structure is different from that used to generate the RF model, stemming from model uncertainty or calibration issues. This phenomenon is rooted in the nature of ensemble methods like RF, which can lead to overfitting and overconfidence in predictions,^[46] especially when faced with out-of-distribution data. The issue of model calibration in machine learning, including Random Forests, has been extensively studied. While RF regression is generally well-calibrated for in-distribution data, it can become miscalibrated when faced with data from different distributions.^[85] Furthermore, Kull et al.^[73] proposed methods to improve the calibration of RF regressions, acknowledging that they can become overconfident if not calibrated adequately. Their work highlights the need for careful consideration of model calibration, especially when working with large datasets or when applying models to data with potentially different distributions. The high R^2 values observed in our study, despite poor generalization in cross-testing, exemplify this issue. As Probst and Boulesteix^[92] point out, 'the out-of-bag error estimate, commonly used in Random Forests, can be overly optimistic,' which may contribute to overconfidence in model performance. These findings underscore the importance of robust validation techniques and careful interpretation of model performance metrics, especially when working with large synthetic datasets that may not fully capture the complexity and variability of real-world data distributions.

Conclusion

The comparison between the rank-based method and the copula-based method for generating synthetic datasets revealed that the rank-based method more effectively preserved the original distribution moments (mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis) and the correlation structure. The rank-based method was more straightforward to implement and provided more consistent results, making it a robust choice for maintaining relational dependencies in synthetic datasets. Conversely, the copula-based method, while flexible and capable of modeling complex dependencies, showed more variability in preserving the original data's characteristics and was more computationally intensive. The differences between the original (COR1) and synthetic (COR2) correlation matrices are mostly minor, with a few moderate discrepancies. These differences are not significant enough to drastically impact the overall distribution structure. The synthetic data generation method effectively maintains the correlation structure and distribution moments, making it a reliable approach for creating synthetic datasets with similar statistical properties to the original data. However, our analyses do not guarantee that artificial relationships between subsets of variables within the synthetic database have not been introduced. These potential artificial relationships could affect certain downstream analyses, and further scrutiny may be necessary to ensure the integrity of the synthetic data for specific applications. Our analyses also indicated that the RF regression consistently outperformed the LM regression with higher precision values, lower SE, and lower AIC values, regardless of whether the variables followed normal or non-normal distributions.

However, while both LM and RF regressions perform well when the synthetic database and the prediction model share the same distributional assumptions, the LM regressions exhibit consistent predictability across different distribution types. In contrast, the RF regressions demonstrate high specificity and significant performance degradation in cross-testing scenarios where the distributional assumptions differ. Furthermore, while key predictors like DMI and EE remain consistently critical in predicting CH₄, the assumption of non-normal distribution reveals potentially essential nuances in the relationship between dietary components (particularly fiber) and CH₄ emissions. This highlights the need for distribution-aware modeling approaches in animal science, especially animal nutrition, to ensure more accurate and robust predictions of CH₄ emissions from ruminants.

List of Abbreviations

ADF = acid detergent fiber; **AI** = artificial intelligence; **AIC** = Akaike's Informational Criterion; **BW** = body weight; **CCC** = concordance correlation coefficient; **C_b** = accuracy; **CH₄** = methane; **CP** = crude protein; **COR1** = correlation matrix of the original database; **COR2** = correlation matrix of the synthetic database; **DL** = deep learning, **DM** = dry matter; **DMI** = dry matter intake; **DP** = differential privacy; **EE** = ether extract; **GAN** = generative adversarial networks; **LM** = linear model; **MB** = mean bias; **ML** = machine learning; **MSE** = mean square error; **MSEP** = mean square error of prediction; **NDF** = neutral detergent fiber; **PAS** = predictive accuracy score; **RF** = random forest; **RMSEP** = root of MSEP; **SD** = standard deviation; **SDV** = synthetic data vault; **SE** = standard error; **SEM** = structural equation modeling; **SER** = square error reduction; and **VAE** = variational autoencoders.

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Conflict of Interest Disclosure

The author declares no financial conflict of interest with the content of this manuscript.

Ethics Approval

No live animal was used in this manuscript.

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Appendix 1. Descriptive statistics of the original data¹.

ID ²	BW	DMI	CP	NDF	EE
1	447	7.95±0.305[7.73,8.17]	13.2±1.41[12.2,14.2]	13.3±0.226[13.1,13.4]	3.91±0.0990[3.84,3.98]
2	467±36.1[430,520]	6.29±1.34[4.58,8.27]	14.9±0.274[14.6,15.1]	37.7±12.1[26.6,48.7]	2.92±0.886[2.11,3.73]
3	392±48.3[345,439]	6.32±0.737[5.34,6.94]	14.2±0.787[13.4,15.1]	26.1±11.5[12.7,36.3]	3.33±0.714[2.40,4.01]
4	260	5.94±0.589[5.07,6.38]	14.6	34.7	3.17
5	380	6.84±1.32[5.37,8.31]	16.4±0.327[16.0,16.8]	27.5±5.92[20.3,34.8]	3.50±0.0816[3.40,3.60]
6	400	8.50±0.446[7.85,8.86]	12.7±0.173[12.4,12.8]	32.8±1.16[31.6,34.3]	5.01±1.70[2.46,5.86]
7	255±0.577[254,255]	5.80±0.0513[5.76,5.86]	16.0	45.1	3.45
8	184±21.7[154,210]	3.68±0.575[2.93,4.31]	20.1±5.63[13.8,26.9]	39.3±10.1[25.2,50.5]	4.24±0.288[4.00,4.60]
9	322±5.74[314,327]	5.31±0.170[5.07,5.45]	12.8±1.75[11.5,15.4]	46.2±9.55[35.4,58.5]	2.57±0.163[2.36,2.70]
10	327±1.41[326,328]	3.82±0.594[3.40,4.24]	11.4±2.21[9.88,13.0]	69.4±4.09[66.5,72.3]	1.89±0.0283[1.87,1.91]
11	400	4.60	15.8	30.6	1.88
12	238±18.6[217,258]	4.99±0.437[4.49,5.39]	22.4±5.91[16.1,28.0]	32.1±12.2[21.6,42.7]	4.20±0.283[4.00,4.60]
13	347±16.9[325,365]	5.61±1.76[3.50,7.60]	11.5	36.7	5.20
14	346±10.9[331,357]	4.98±0.585[4.30,5.70]	8.68±0.737[7.80,9.60]	61.1±1.15[59.5,62.1]	3.88±2.04[1.00,5.70]
15	332±4.95[328,335]	4.50±0.0636[4.45,4.54]	14.8	31.2	4.00
16	352±16.3[340,363]	4.80	13.9±0.212[13.7,14.0]	20.9	3.20±0.375[2.93,3.46]
17	482±2.06[480,484]	6.77±0.274[6.43,7.10]	11.8	21.7	3.50
18	614±8.83[608,627]	6.82±3.51[2.76,10.9]	13.8	20.1	2.07
19	286]	3.84	17.5	50.0	2.55
20	513±12.2[495,526]	8.11±0.474[7.54,8.65]	12.5±0.312[12.0,12.8]	34.2±5.97[28.0,40.6]	3.23±0.327[2.90,3.73]
21	357±4.73[352,361]	4.27±0.0613[4.20,4.32]	20.0±3.19[16.4,22.4]	37.5±1.98[35.7,39.6]	10.0±6.65[2.80,15.9]
22	218	5.20±0.0862[5.10,5.31]	15.2±2.39[13.1,17.4]	15.3±3.08[11.5,18.8]	6.46±0.240[6.25,6.68]
23	324±4.65[320,330]	6.23±0.299[5.80,6.50]	16.5±3.27[13.3,20.2]	17.1±1.95[14.5,18.7]	6.85±1.21[5.80,8.30]
24	362	7.38±0.253[7.09,7.71]	18.5±0.377[18.1,19.0]	17.0±2.69[14.4,20.3]	5.50±0.294[5.20,5.90]

ID ²	BW	DMI	CP	NDF	EE
25	503	7.74±0.579[6.88,8.11]	13.3±0.940[12.7,14.7]	12.1±0.446[11.6,12.5]	3.37±0.263[3.06,3.67]
26	464	7.80±0.581[7.29,8.61]	20.1±2.43[17.8,22.4]	19.4±2.31[17.1,21.4]	6.87±0.839[6.12,7.70]
27	479±7.83[471,489]	7.11±0.198[6.90,7.32]	15.0±0.0350[15.0,15.1]	13.4±0.302[13.2,13.9]	6.26±2.53[3.00,8.71]
28	407±47.1[361,454]	7.93±0.947[7.03,9.46]	15.4±1.49[14.4,18.1]	33.1±4.07[26.7,38.5]	4.43±0.810[3.56,5.53]
29	279±12.0[270,287]	6.05±0.919[5.40,6.70]	11.4±1.91[10.0,12.7]	50.6±2.26[49.0,52.2]	3.95±1.91[2.60,5.30]
30	493±41.0[448,556]	6.52±1.28[5.30,8.22]	8.63	66.8	2.34
31	290	5.28±1.52[3.64,7.77]	18.7±0.765[17.5,19.3]	45.5±3.74[42.0,49.0]	2.65±0.267[2.40,2.90]
32	388	8.54±0.384[8.13,9.05]	19.3±4.66[13.0,23.5]	34.6±2.70[32.5,38.5]	4.43±1.28[3.00,5.60]
33	529	9.39±0.593[8.76,10.2]	19.3±4.93[12.2,23.1]	24.1±3.50[19.4,27.9]	3.90±1.63[2.00,5.40]
34	326±74.8[261,391]	4.24±2.25[2.29,6.23]	16.7±3.29[13.8,19.5]	19.6±0.231[19.4,19.8]	4.05±0.635[3.50,4.60]
35	176±0.707[175,176]	3.98±0.0919[3.91,4.04]	15.6	39.9	4.76
36	461±114[315,575]	7.37±0.726[6.64,8.27]	13.7±0.122[13.5,13.8]	53.8±0.917[52.7,54.8]	4.34
37	459	7.26±0.971[5.93,8.55]	15.1±0.825[13.9,16.2]	44.3±6.83[34.5,53.0]	2.43±0.164[2.27,2.70]
38	140±7.21[134,148]	2.83±0.153[2.74,3.01]	9.77±0.115[9.70,9.90]	54.0±9.01[45.2,63.2]	5.90
39	366±13.6[353,380]	5.99±2.09[3.58,7.31]	10.4±8.78[2.40,19.8]	55.7±31.0[20.0,75.3]	1.67±0.586[1.00,2.10]
40	526±1.55[525,528]	8.63±0.171[8.40,8.80]	12.5±0.0577[12.4,12.5]	38.3±0.330[37.9,38.6]	3.46±0.0299[3.42,3.49]
41	312	7.28±0.342[6.79,7.71]	14.5	36.2	3.73±1.51[3.20,7.46]
42	141	4.15±0.318[3.92,4.37]	12.9	47.3	5.60
43	599	6.28±0.0954[6.19,6.38]	8.87±0.153[8.70,9.00]	45.3±3.48[42.6,49.2]	2.83±0.153[2.70,3.00]
44	508±17.9[495,528]	8.67±0.0208[8.65,8.68]	13.3	19.9	4.64
45	180±12.6[161,193]	3.56±0.670[2.70,4.33]	10.5±0.272[10.1,10.9]	53.6±2.72[50.5,56.8]	2.14±0.463[1.61,2.82]
46	604±34.3[551,662]	9.70±2.07[7.60,12.2]	18.5±0.920[17.4,19.6]	44.3±1.39[41.7,45.3]	2.08±0.103[1.90,2.20]
47	321±11.7[308,335]	5.66±1.85[3.60,7.78]	17.1±0.535[16.6,17.7]	31.5±9.87[20.6,41.3]	2.48±0.419[2.20,3.10]
48	549	8.50	11.7	37.6	2.70
49	637	7.15	11.3	38.6	1.85

ID ²	BW	DMI	CP	NDF	EE
50	325	4.07	10.9	18.8	4.39
51	213±1.41[212,214]	4.65±0.205[4.50,4.79]	25.7±2.23[24.1,27.2]	17.7±1.62[16.6,18.9]	2.29±0.0141[2.28,2.30]
52	294±27.9[269,324]	4.63±1.03[3.50,5.50]	10.6	36.3	3.50
53	375	4.97±0.751[4.10,5.40]	13.1±1.14[12.3,14.4]	43.8±18.3[24.3,60.5]	4.59±0.695[4.03,5.37]
54	722±12.0[713,730]	10.5±0.283[10.3,10.7]	14.5±0.141[14.4,14.6]	28.5±0.636[28.0,28.9]	3.96±1.75[2.72,5.20]
55	269±6.84[256,276]	4.59±0.150[4.33,4.77]	18.2±4.11[11.8,24.4]	59.2±12.7[39.6,73.1]	4.05±0.818[2.97,5.51]
56	305±10.1[291,315]	5.50±1.00[4.60,6.60]	21.9±2.66[19.6,24.2]	49.5±14.2[37.2,61.8]	5.80±0.346[5.50,6.10]
57	600	8.64±0.640[7.78,9.30]	12.1	40.7	3.00
58	477±9.84[462,482]	7.60±0.796[6.50,8.40]	13.1	38.2	3.60
59	372	7.28±1.01[6.23,8.70]	13.9±0.657[13.3,14.5]	34.4±8.05[27.0,41.7]	3.42±0.361[3.09,3.75]
60	397±90.1[319,475]	6.96±0.704[6.09,7.55]	13.0±0.866[12.2,13.7]	27.8±9.93[19.2,36.4]	2.79±0.606[2.26,3.31]
61	334±3.32[330,338]	6.86±0.405[6.31,7.29]	18.8±3.75[15.5,22.0]	41.4±0.523[40.9,41.9]	3.71±1.33[2.55,4.88]
62	452±4.24[449,455]	3.47	13.8	15.7	6.32
63	275±1.60[273,276]	5.10	9.93±1.17[7.88,11.1]	56.6±6.22[50.5,68.1]	2.70±0.470[1.94,3.18]

¹ Values represent average ± standard deviation [minimum, maximum].

² 1=Archibeque et al. ^[4], 2= Baber et al. ^[7], 3=Beauchemin and McGinn ^[8], 4=Beauchemin and McGinn ^[10], 5=Beauchemin and McGinn ^[9], 6=Beauchemin et al. ^[12], 7=^[11], 8=Beever et al. ^[14], 9=Beever et al. ^[13], 10=Birkelo et al. ^[16], 11=Boadi et al. ^[17], 12=Cammell et al. ^[22], 13=Chaokaur et al. ^[25], 14=Chuntrakort et al. ^[26], 15=Cole and McCroskey ^[27], 16=Croka and Wagner ^[28], 17=Crossland et al. ^[29], 18=Delfino et al. ^[30], 19=Derno et al. ^[31], 20=Fuller et al. ^[39], 21=Haaland et al. ^[47], 22=Hales et al. ^[49], 23=Hales et al. ^[50], 24=Hales et al. ^[48], 25=Hales et al. ^[51], 26=Hales et al. ^[53], 27=Hales et al. ^[52], 28=Hammond et al. ^[54], 29=Hellwing et al. ^[58], 30=Hemphill et al. ^[59], 31=Hironaka et al. ^[61], 32=Hünerberg et al. ^[65], 33=Hünerberg et al. ^[64], 34=Jennings et al. ^[66], 35=Jiao et al. ^[67], 36=Jiao et al. ^[68], 37=Kirkpatrick et al. ^[71], 38=Kongphitee et al. ^[72], 39=Kurihara et al. ^[74], 40=Lee et al. ^[75], 41=McGinn et al. ^[78], 42=Mohammed et al. ^[81], 43=Nishida et al. ^[87], 44=Nkrumah et al. ^[88], 45=Ortigue et al. ^[89], 46=Reynolds and Tyrrell ^[95], 47=Reynolds et al. ^[96], 48=Romero-Perez et al. ^[98], 49=Romero-Perez et al. ^[99], 50=Rumpler et al. ^[100], 51=Shreck et al. ^[102], 52=Tangjitwattanachai et al. ^[108], 53=Thornton and Owens ^[117], 54=Troy et al. ^[119], 55=Tyrrell et al. ^[120], 56=Varga et al. ^[124], 57=Vyas et al. ^[126], 58=Vyas et al. ^[127], 59=Vyas et al. ^[125], 60=Vyas et al. ^[128], 61=Waldo et al. ^[129], 62=Walter et al. ^[130], and 63=Wei et al. ^[133]

Appendix 1. Descriptive statistics of the original data¹ (continued).

ID ²	Starch	CH ₄	OM	ADF
1	64.4±2.54[62.6,66.2]	126±20.5[111,140]	89.3	6.11±0.127[6.02,6.20]
2	30.9±25.6[7.49,54.3]	121±29.5[83.3,167]	---	---
3	40.9±14.3[27.3,58.3]	111±49.1[62.1,171]	94.0±0.913[92.7,94.8]	10.2±6.40[3.50,16.3]
4	14.5	150±28.6[108,171]	91.0	21.1
5	30.4±12.6[14.9,45.8]	142±23.8[114,169]	93.3±0.776[92.3,94.2]	16.7±4.16[11.6,21.8]
6	27.0	151±23.7[120,177]	91.6±0.938[90.8,92.6]	19.1±1.45[17.5,21.0]
7	15.0	99.2±0.503[98.7,99.7]	91.4	26.1
8	0	93.5±16.1[66.3,108]	---	---
9	13.4±17.2[0,35.8]	135±13.6[117,150]	---	---
10	0	75.5±17.2[63.4,87.7]	---	---
11	20.3]	93.7	91.3	21.5
12	0	80.1±9.09[70.0,90.4]	---	---
13	30.3	145±21.2[121,168]	---	---
14	14.9±4.30[9.99,20.0]	110±48.2[65.8,170]	---	---
15	50.0	67.3±13.9[57.5,77.1]	95.3	15.4
16	56.0	56.5±8.72[50.4,62.7]	---	---
17	49.2	50.5±4.06[45.8,55.1]	---	---
18	31.0	158±63.2[86.1,240]	90.8	9.81
19	0	100	---	---
20	30.7±9.94[21.1,45.3]	140±30.8[104,174]	---	---
21	11.3±13.6[3.10,27.0]	82.1±12.1[71.3,95.2]	---	---
22	46.1±4.22[41.3,50.9]	47.0±3.91[42.6,52.1]	---	---
23	50.3±11.0[39.1,60.7]	59.0±10.6[51.1,73.6]	---	---
24	50.5±3.54[46.4,54.6]	93.5±10.2[80.3,103]	---	---

ID ²	Starch	CH ₄	OM	ADF
25	55.9±4.91[50.2,61.6]	108±5.23[103,115]	---	---
26	35.5±11.5[21.4,46.5]	84.9±7.03[78.8,94.7]	---	---
27	53.9±2.36[51.5,56.9]	67.6±12.3[55.3,80.3]	---	---
28	21.1±8.20[10.0,32.9]	200±11.0[184,220]	95.6±0.849[94.7,96.8]	22.5±3.44[17.1,26.8]
29	10.3±0.354[10.0,10.5]	135±24.0[118,152]	93.4±0.566[93.0,93.8]	---
30	4.11	122±8.63[114,133]	---	---
31	2.00	212±31.6[184,261]	88.0	35.0±4.28[31.0,39.0]
32	22.0±9.23[16.8,35.8]	194±23.6[174,228]	91.8±0.350[91.6,92.3]	22.1±2.73[18.0,23.7]
33	38.7±10.9[31.9,55.0]	131±11.6[119,144]	94.8±0.842[94.0,95.6]	12.0±3.20[7.30,14.2]
34	47.4±2.94[44.8,49.9]	64.3±16.8[49.0,81.7]	---	---
35	21.6	93.6±4.38[90.5,96.7]	---	---
36	7.86	175±14.2[159,194]	---	---
37	24.9±15.3[0,42.8]	174±40.4[116,226]	---	---
38	20.3±11.5[8.83,31.8]	53.1±4.18[50.7,57.9]	---	---
39	13.5±23.3[0,40.4]	135±66.0[71.3,203]	---	---
40	39.6±0.369[39.2,40.1]	167±17.0[145,183]	---	---
41	14.5	165±16.3[129,181]	91.9	16.9
42	16.7	81.2±18.9[67.8,94.5]	90.8	28.1
43	32.6	148±6.83[142,155]	94.5±0.379[94.1,94.8]	27.2±3.79[24.5,31.5]
44	57.2	122±19.9[99.2,136]	---	---
45	14.2±0.946[13.1,15.4]	88.0±12.7[74.7,101]	---	---
46	15.9±2.28[13.9,19.6]	213±46.2[159,268]	90.4±0.892[89.2,91.8]	26.7±1.19[25.2,27.8]
47	34.9±17.3[19.9,49.8]	104±32.5[65.0,142]	---	---
48	31.8	207	92.9	20.6
49	33.8	158	92.5	22.4

ID ²	Starch	CH ₄	OM	ADF
50	57.6	83.3±5.68[72.1,89.4]	96.7	9.20
51	6.18±8.74[0,12.4]	86.1±8.17[80.4,91.9]	---	---
52	30.9	131±20.4[109,148]	---	---
53	29.1±17.5[11.4,46.4]	155±21.9[133,177]	91.1±1.46[89.8,92.7]	26.1±14.0[11.5,39.5]
54	27.6±1.91[26.2,28.9]	249±4.24[246,252]	94.7±0.0707[94.6,94.7]	19.5±0.141[19.4,19.6]
55	5.24±4.16[0.800,11.0]	96.8±9.18[78.6,110]	91.9±1.28[90.2,93.6]	40.7±4.14[34.3,46.3]
56	0	127±20.0[105,145]	---	---
57	18.4	188±15.9[172,210]	90.5	21.3
58	22.5	178±10.1[167,190]	92.9	24.8
59	22.4±9.50[13.7,31.0]	133±15.3[111,154]	94.6±1.70[93.0,96.1]	13.2±6.52[7.20,19.1]
60	41.9±17.5[26.7,57.0]	135±33.3[102,176]	94.3±1.27[93.2,95.4]	15.4±8.08[8.40,22.4]
61	14.6±13.4[3.00,26.2]	168±11.8[158,182]	93.5±1.36[92.3,94.7]	27.5±4.25[23.8,31.5]
62	53.3	28.6±5.03[25.0,32.2]	---	---
63	28.0±9.16[14.9,37.4]	108±9.49[92.7,118]	---	---

¹ Values represent average ± standard deviation [minimum, maximum].

² 1=Archibeque et al. ^[4], 2= Baber et al. ^[7], 3=Beauchemin and McGinn ^[8], 4=Beauchemin and McGinn ^[10], 5=Beauchemin and McGinn ^[9], 6=Beauchemin et al. ^[12], 7=^[11], 8=Beever et al. ^[14], 9=Beever et al. ^[13], 10=Birkelo et al. ^[16], 11=Boadi et al. ^[17], 12=Cammell et al. ^[22], 13=Chaokaur et al. ^[25], 14=Chuntrakort et al. ^[26], 15=Cole and McCroskey ^[27], 16=Croka and Wagner ^[28], 17=Crossland et al. ^[29], 18=Delfino et al. ^[30], 19=Derno et al. ^[31], 20=Fuller et al. ^[39], 21=Haaland et al. ^[47], 22=Hales et al. ^[49], 23=Hales et al. ^[50], 24=Hales et al. ^[48], 25=Hales et al. ^[51], 26=Hales et al. ^[53], 27=Hales et al. ^[52], 28=Hammond et al. ^[54], 29=Hellwing et al. ^[58], 30=Hemphill et al. ^[59], 31=Hironaka et al. ^[61], 32=Hünerberg et al. ^[65], 33=Hünerberg et al. ^[64], 34=Jennings et al. ^[66], 35=Jiao et al. ^[67], 36=Jiao et al. ^[68], 37=Kirkpatrick et al. ^[71], 38=Kongphitee et al. ^[72], 39=Kurihara et al. ^[74], 40=Lee et al. ^[75], 41=McGinn et al. ^[78], 42=Mohammed et al. ^[81], 43=Nishida et al. ^[87], 44=Nkrumah et al. ^[88], 45=Ortignes et al. ^[89], 46=Reynolds and Tyrrell ^[95], 47=Reynolds et al. ^[96], 48=Romero-Perez et al. ^[98], 49=Romero-Perez et al. ^[99], 50=Rumpler et al. ^[100], 51=Shreck et al. ^[102], 52=Tangjitwattanachai et al. ^[108], 53=Thornton and Owens ^[117], 54=Troy et al. ^[119], 55=Tyrrell et al. ^[120], 56=Varga et al. ^[124], 57=Vyas et al. ^[126], 58=Vyas et al. ^[127], 59=Vyas et al. ^[125], 60=Vyas et al. ^[128], 61=Waldo et al. ^[129], 62=Walter et al. ^[130], and 63=Wei et al. ^[133]

Appendix 2. R-script code to fit a distribution to the data and generate synthetic data based on the best fit.

```
getDist <- function(var, varname = "", normalonly = FALSE, hist = TRUE, n = 10000, showtime = F, showtitle = F, ...)  
{  
  # Function to fit a distribution to the data and generate synthetic data based on the best fit.  
  # If normalonly is TRUE, it fits a normal distribution regardless of the data.  
  # If hist is TRUE, it generates a histogram comparing the original and synthetic data.  
  # The number of samples to generate is specified by n.  
  
  require(gamlss)  
  
  # Fit the best distribution  
  if (normalonly == FALSE) {  
    m1 <- fitDist(var, ...)  
  } else {  
    m1 <- gamlss(var ~ 1, family = "NO")  
  }  
  
  aic <- m1$aic  
  pars <- m1$parameters  
  lpar <- length(m1$parameters)  
  dis <- paste0("r", m1$family[[1]])  
  
  # Generate the synthetic data based on the fitted distribution  
  outdis <- switch(lpar,  
    call(dis, n = n, mu = fitted(m1)[1]),  
    call(dis, n = n, mu = fitted(m1)[1], sigma = fitted(m1, "sigma")[1]),  
    call(dis, n = n, mu = fitted(m1)[1], sigma = fitted(m1, "sigma")[1], nu =  
fitted(m1, "nu")[1]),  
    call(dis, n = n, mu = fitted(m1)[1], sigma = fitted(m1, "sigma")[1], nu =  
fitted(m1, "nu")[1], tau = fitted(m1, "tau")[1])  
  )  
  
  # Create a description of the fitted distribution  
  txtdis <- switch(lpar,  
    paste(dis, "(n=", n, ", \u03BC=", formatC(fitted(m1)[1], format = "f",  
digits = 4), ")", sep = ""),  
    paste(dis, "(n=", n, ", \u03BC=", formatC(fitted(m1)[1], format = "f",  
digits = 4), ", \u03C3=", formatC(fitted(m1, "sigma")[1], format = "f", digits = 4), ")", sep  
= ""),  
    paste(dis, "(n=", n, ", \u03BC=", formatC(fitted(m1)[1], format = "f",  
digits = 4), ", \u03C3=", formatC(fitted(m1, "sigma")[1], format = "f", digits = 4), ",  
\u03BD=", formatC(fitted(m1, "nu")[1], format = "f", digits = 4), ")", sep = ""),  
    paste(dis, "(n=", n, ", \u03BC=", formatC(fitted(m1)[1], format = "f",  
digits = 4), ", \u03C3=", formatC(fitted(m1, "sigma")[1], format = "f", digits = 4), ",  
\u03BD=", formatC(fitted(m1, "nu")[1], format = "f", digits = 4), ", \u03C4=",  
formatC(fitted(m1, "tau")[1], format = "f", digits = 4), ")", sep = "")  
  )  
  
  outval <- try(eval(outdis), silent = TRUE)
```

```

# Fallback to normal distribution if fitting fails
if (class(outval) == "try-error") {
  mu <- mean(var)
  sd <- sd(var)
  outdis <- paste("rnorm, ", n, ", ", mu, ", ", sd, sep = "")
  subtitle <- paste("Best-fit distribution: ", txtdis, " !FAILED!\n", "Adopted distribution:
rnorm(n=", n, ", mu=", formatC(mu, format = "f", digits = 4), ", sigma=", formatC(sd, format =
"f", digits = 4), ")", sep = "")
  txtdis <- paste(txtdis, " !FAILED! | rnorm(n=", n, ", mu=", formatC(mu, format = "f",
digits = 4), ", sigma=", formatC(sd, format = "f", digits = 4), ")", sep = "")
  outval <- rnorm(n, mu, sd)
  aic <- Inf
} else {
  subtitle <- paste("Best-fit distribution: ", txtdis, sep = "")
}

# Generate histogram and density plots if requested
if (hist) {
  densMode <- function(x, x_target=0) {
    td <- density(x)
    maxDens <- which.max(td$y)
    density_at_target <- approx(td$x, td$y, xout = x_target)$y
    list(x = td$x[maxDens], y = td$y[maxDens], target = density_at_target)
  }

  d <- as.data.frame(var)
  mean_value <- mean(d$var)
  sd_value <- sd(d$var)
  min_value <- min(d$var)
  max_value <- max(d$var)
  atmode <- densMode(d$var)$y
  atmin <- densMode(d$var,min_value)$target
  atmax <- densMode(d$var,max_value)$target
  at1SDm <- densMode(d$var,mean_value-sd_value)$target
  at1SDp <- densMode(d$var,mean_value+sd_value)$target
  annotations <- data.frame(
    x = c(round(min_value, 2), round(mean_value, 2), round(max_value, 2), round(mean_value -
sd_value, 2), round(mean_value + sd_value, 2)),
    y = c(atmin, atmode, atmax, at1SDm, at1SDp),
    label = c("Min\n", "\u0058\u0304 \n", "Max\n", "\u0058\u0304-SD \n", "
\u0058\u0304+SD\n")
  )

  # Set title and caption based on the parameters
  title_text <- if (showtitle) paste("Histogram and Density Plots of '", varname, "'", sep =
"") else NULL
  caption_text <- if (showtime) paste(format(Sys.time(), "%A, %d %b %Y, %X"), sep = "") else
NULL

  plot <- ggplot() +
    geom_histogram(data = d, aes(x = var, y = after_stat(density)), color = "#0066CC", fill
= "#0099F8") +
    geom_density(data = d, aes(x = var), color = "#CC3300", fill = "#F85700", alpha = 0.5) +
    geom_density(data = as.data.frame(outval), aes(x = outval), color = "#00897B", linewidth
= 1.5) +
    geom_text(data = annotations, aes(x = x, y = y, label = paste(label, x)), size = 4,
hjust = c(1.1, 1.1, -0.1, 1.1, -0.1), fontface = "bold") +

```

```

    labs(title = title_text, subtitle = subtitle, caption = caption_text, x = varname, y =
"Density") +
    theme_classic() +
    theme(
      plot.title = element_text(color = "#0099F8", size = 16, face = "bold"),
      plot.subtitle = element_text(color = "#00897B", size = 11, face = "bold"),
      axis.title.x = element_text(size = 10, face = "bold"),
      axis.title.y = element_text(size = 10, face = "bold"),
      axis.text.x = element_text(size = 10),
      axis.text.y = element_text(size = 10),
      plot.caption = element_text(face = "italic")
    ) +
    geom_vline(aes(xintercept = mean(var)), color = "#303F9F", linewidth = 1) +
    geom_vline(aes(xintercept = mean(var) + sd(var)), color = "#303F9F", linewidth = 0.75,
linetype = "dashed") +
    geom_vline(aes(xintercept = mean(var) - sd(var)), color = "#303F9F", linewidth = 0.75,
linetype = "dashed") +
    geom_vline(aes(xintercept = min(var)), color = "#303F9F", linewidth = 0.5, linetype =
"dashed") +
    geom_vline(aes(xintercept = max(var)), color = "#303F9F", linewidth = 0.5, linetype =
"dashed")

    # Save the plot as a TIFF file
    tiff(paste(varname, ".tiff", sep = ""), width = 8000, height = 8000, bg = "white", res =
800, compress = "lzw")
    print(plot)
    dev.off()
  }

  return(list(dist = txtdis, aic = aic, distval = outval))
}

# Load necessary libraries
library(gamlss)
library(ggplot2)

# Example dataset: Simulate some non-normal data
set.seed(123)
example_data <- rnorm(1000, mean = 50, sd = 10)

# Use the getDist function to fit a distribution and generate synthetic data
result <- getDist(var = example_data, varname = "Example Data", normalonly = FALSE, hist =
TRUE, n = 10000)

# Print the results
print(result$dist)
print(result$aic)

# Display the first few synthetic data values
head(result$distval)

```

Appendix 3. R-script code for implementing rank-based and copula methods for correlating multi-normally distributed variables using Cholesky decomposition.

```
# Function to apply rank-based adjustment
correlate_using_ranks <- function(varmatrix, cormatrix)
{
  require(MASS)

  n <- nrow(varmatrix)
  ncols <- ncol(varmatrix)

  # Generate uncorrelated normally distributed columns
  mu <- rep(0, ncols)
  sigma <- diag(ncols)
  d <- mvrnorm(n, mu, sigma)

  # Correlate the normally distributed columns
  u <- chol(cormatrix)
  z <- d %%% u

  # Rank each column
  rank_z <- apply(z, 2, rank)
  rank_varmatrix <- apply(varmatrix, 2, rank)

  # Allocate original values based on correlated ranks
  z2 <- matrix(NA, n, ncols)
  for (i in 1:ncols) {
    z2[, i] <- varmatrix[match(rank_z[, i], rank_varmatrix[, i]), i]
  }

  return(z2)
}

# Function to apply copula adjustment
correlate_using_copula <- function(varmatrix, cormatrix, iterations = 100, tol = 1e-5)
{
  library(MASS)
  library(copula)

  n <- nrow(varmatrix)
  ncols <- ncol(varmatrix)

  # Standardize the variables to uniform marginals
  uniform_data <- apply(varmatrix, 2, function(x) rank(x) / (length(x) + 1))

  # Transform to normal marginals
  normal_data <- qnorm(uniform_data)

  # Initialize correlated data
  correlated_data <- normal_data

  for (iteration in 1:iterations) {
    # Calculate current correlation
    current_corr <- cor(correlated_data)

    # Decompose the desired correlation matrix
```

```

L <- chol(cormatrix)
current_L <- chol(current_corr)

# Adjust using Cholesky factors
adjustment <- correlated_data %*% solve(current_L) %*% L
correlated_data <- adjustment %*% t(L)

# Transform back to original marginals
for (i in 1:ncols) {
  ranks <- rank(correlated_data[, i])
  correlated_data[, i] <- sort(varmatrix[, i])[ranks]
}

# Check convergence
if (iteration %% 5 == 0 && max(abs(cor(correlated_data) - cormatrix)) < tol) {
  break
}
}

return(correlated_data)
}

# Testing
# Generate synthetic non-normal data
set.seed(1983458)
n_samples <- 5000
var1 <- rchisq(n_samples, df = 2)
var2 <- rbeta(n_samples, shape1 = 2, shape2 = 5)
var3 <- rlnorm(n_samples, meanlog = 0, sdlog = 1)
varmatrix <- cbind(var1, var2, var3)

# Create a predefined positive-definite correlation matrix
cormatrix <- matrix(c(
  1, 0.5, 0.3,
  0.5, 1, 0.4,
  0.3, 0.4, 1
), nrow = 3, ncol = 3)

# Apply the adjustment functions
correlated_data_copula <- correlate_using_copula(varmatrix, cormatrix, 500)
correlated_data_ranks <- correlate_using_ranks(varmatrix, cormatrix)

# Verify the correlation matrix
cor(correlated_data_copula)
cor(correlated_data_ranks)

```

Appendix 4. R-script code for comparing distribution correlation and moments between rank-based and copula methods, using 100 iterations. Replace [username] with the appropriate folder name.

```
library(MASS)
library(boot)
library(stats)
library(moments)
library(ggplot2)
library(reshape2)

# Generate a positive-definite correlation matrix
generate_pos_def_corr_matrix <- function(n) {
  matrix <- matrix(rnorm(n^2), n, n)
  corr_matrix <- cov2cor(matrix %% t(matrix))
  return(corr_matrix)
}

# Calculate moments
calculate_moments <- function(data) {
  mean <- colMeans(data)
  variance <- apply(data, 2, var)
  skewness <- apply(data, 2, skewness)
  kurtosis <- apply(data, 2, kurtosis)
  moments <- data.frame(mean, variance, skewness, kurtosis)
  return(moments)
}

# Reduce sample size for faster computation
n_samples <- 5000
iterations <- 100
n_vars <- 3
corr_diff_values_rank <- list()
corr_diff_values_copula <- list()
original_moments_list <- list()
correlated_moments_rank_list <- list()
correlated_moments_copula_list <- list()

for (i in 1:n_vars) {
  for (j in i:n_vars) {
    corr_diff_values_rank[[paste0("Var", i, "-Var", j)]] <- numeric()
    corr_diff_values_copula[[paste0("Var", i, "-Var", j)]] <- numeric()
  }
}

for (iter in 1:iterations) {
  cat(paste("Iteration: ", iter, "\n"))
  # Generate synthetic non-normal data
  var1 <- rchisq(n_samples, df = 2)
  var2 <- rbeta(n_samples, shape1 = 2, shape2 = 5)
  var3 <- rlnorm(n_samples, meanlog = 0, sdlog = 1)
  varmatrix <- cbind(var1, var2, var3)

  # Use a predefined positive-definite correlation matrix
  cormatrix <- matrix(c(
    1, 0.5, 0.3,
    0.5, 1, 0.4,
```

```

    0.3, 0.4, 1
  ), nrow = 3, ncol = 3)
# Create a random positive-definite correlation matrix
#cormatrix <- generate_pos_def_corr_matrix(n_vars)

# Apply the rank-based function
correlated_data_rank <- correlate_using_ranks(varmatrix, cormatrix)
# Apply the copula-based function
correlated_data_copula <- correlate_using_copula(varmatrix, cormatrix)

# Calculate the Spearman correlation matrices of the correlated data
corr_matrix_rank <- cor(correlated_data_rank, method = "spearman")
corr_matrix_copula <- cor(correlated_data_copula, method = "spearman")

# Calculate the differences for the rank-based approach
for (i in 1:n_vars) {
  for (j in i:n_vars) {
    corr_diff_values_rank[[paste0("Var", i, "-Var", j)]] <-
c(corr_diff_values_rank[[paste0("Var", i, "-Var", j)]], cormatrix[i, j] - corr_matrix_rank[i,
j])
  }
}

# Calculate the differences for the copula-based approach
for (i in 1:n_vars) {
  for (j in i:n_vars) {
    corr_diff_values_copula[[paste0("Var", i, "-Var", j)]] <-
c(corr_diff_values_copula[[paste0("Var", i, "-Var", j)]], cormatrix[i, j] -
corr_matrix_copula[i, j])
  }
}

# Calculate moments
original_moments_list[[iter]] <- calculate_moments(varmatrix)
correlated_moments_rank_list[[iter]] <- calculate_moments(correlated_data_rank)
correlated_moments_copula_list[[iter]] <- calculate_moments(correlated_data_copula)
}

# Convert moments lists to data frames
original_moments_df <- do.call(rbind, original_moments_list)
correlated_moments_rank_df <- do.call(rbind, correlated_moments_rank_list)
correlated_moments_copula_df <- do.call(rbind, correlated_moments_copula_list)

# Plot histograms of the differences for the rank-based approach
pdf("c:/users/[username]/desktop/correlation_diff_histograms_rank.pdf", width = 14, height =
14)
par(mfrow = c(n_vars, n_vars))
for (i in 1:n_vars) {
  for (j in 1:n_vars) {
    if (i <= j) {
      hist(corr_diff_values_rank[[paste0("Var", i, "-Var", j)]], main = paste0("Rank-based
Correlation Difference: Var", i, "-Var", j), xlab = "Difference", xlim = c(-1, 1), breaks =
30)
    }
  }
}
dev.off()

```

```

# Plot histograms of the differences for the copula-based approach
pdf("c:/users/[username]/desktop/correlation_diff_histograms_copula.pdf", width = 14, height =
14)
par(mfrow = c(n_vars, n_vars))
for (i in 1:n_vars) {
  for (j in 1:n_vars) {
    if (i <= j) {
      hist(corr_diff_values_copula[[paste0("Var", i, "-Var", j)]], main = paste0("Copula-based
Correlation Difference: Var", i, "-Var", j), xlab = "Difference", xlim = c(-1, 1), breaks =
30)
    }
  }
}
dev.off()

# Calculate and print min and max for correlation differences
min_max_corr_diff <- function(corr_diff_list, method) {
  for (i in 1:n_vars) {
    for (j in i:n_vars) {
      diff_values <- corr_diff_list[[paste0("Var", i, "-Var", j)]]
      cat(method, " - Var", i, "-Var", j, " Min: ", min(diff_values), " Max: ",
max(diff_values), "\n")
    }
  }
}

cat("Rank-based Correlation Differences:\n")
min_max_corr_diff(corr_diff_values_rank, "Rank-based")

cat("\nCopula-based Correlation Differences:\n")
min_max_corr_diff(corr_diff_values_copula, "Copula-based")

# Plot moments
plot_moments <- function(original_moments, correlated_moments, method) {
  original_melt <- melt(original_moments)
  correlated_melt <- melt(correlated_moments)
  original_melt$Method <- "Original"
  correlated_melt$Method <- method

  moments_df <- rbind(original_melt, correlated_melt)

  ggplot(moments_df, aes(x = variable, y = value, fill = Method)) +
    geom_boxplot() +
    facet_wrap(~variable, scales = "free") +
    labs(title = paste(method, "Moments Comparison"), x = "Variable", y = "Value") +
    theme_minimal()
}

pdf("c:/users/[username]/desktop/moments_comparison_rank.pdf", width = 14, height = 10)
print(plot_moments(original_moments_df, correlated_moments_rank_df, "Rank-based"))
dev.off()

pdf("c:/users/[username]/desktop/moments_comparison_copula.pdf", width = 14, height = 10)
print(plot_moments(original_moments_df, correlated_moments_copula_df, "Copula-based"))
dev.off()

```

Supplement 1. Histogram and density plots for acid detergent fiber (ADF, % DM), ash, body weight (BW, kg), crude protein (CP, % DM), dry matter intake (DMI, kg/d), ether extract (EE, % DM), neutral detergent fiber (NDF, % DM), and starch (% DM) from the literature-gathered database. The blue bars represent the histogram, the orange shade indicates the density plot of the original data, the green line illustrates the density plot of the fitted data using the best-fit distribution shown at the top of the plot, and the vertical lines from left to right denote the minimum (min), mean $- 1$ SD, mean, mean $+ 1$ SD, and maximum (max) values in the literature-gathered database.

